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STUDENTS' ENTRY QUALIFICATION IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN GENERAL ENGLISH IN COLLEGES OF EDUCATION IN KWARA STATE

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KEYWORDS: Students' entry qualification, academic performance, English language and General English

ABSTRACT

The paper employed descriptive survey study of students' entry qualification in English language and academic performance in General English in the Colleges of Education in Kwara State, Nigeria. One hundred and eighty- six students were sampled for the study. Descriptive Statistic and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient were used to analyze the data collected. The results showed correlation between students' entry qualification in English language and academic performance in General English. The paper concluded that early good academic performance could enhance future academic performance. Some recommendations were suggested at the end of the study.

INTRODUCTION

Akale (1991) averred that students' academic performance is the level of knowledge, skills or accomplishments in an area of endeavor such as in English language. Brown (1999) referred to it as how students deal with their studies and how they cope with it or accomplish different tasks given to them by their teachers.

Ayodele (2002) pointed out that students performance in English language at the Senior School Certificate Examinations have been persistently poor in the past 20 years. Iliyas (2013) on students' academic performance in General English among students in Colleges of Education in Kwara State revealed that the inability of Colleges of Education students to take a meaningful note from lecture has been a reflection of their poor English background.

On the basis of students' entry qualification, Momoh-olle (1992) and Sear (1983) were of the opinion that students' academic performance is very complex to predict. Despite the complexity associated with students' entry qualification in determining future academic performance of students, some have investigated the issue.

Momoh-Olle(1992) revealed a cogent statistical relationship between students' entry qualification and their academic performance in education theory, language and vocational studies. Ojetunde (1988) articulated a high positive correlation between entry qualification and success.

Gbore (2013) was of the opinion that there was moderate correlation coefficient between SSCE and academic performance of the University undergraduate students which tossed the same direction with the findings of WAEC (1992) that a positive and significant relationship existed between candidates' performance in the SSCE and academic performance in the Universities' undergraduate levels.

Idika (1997) noted a non-significant difference between final performance of WASSCE Technical and GCE holders in their Technical Education programmes. Majasan and Bakare (1979) revealed something close to the findings of Idika; they keenly noted that entry qualification was poor predictor of academic performance and that the degree of performance cannot be linked to the quality of grade obtained in the entry qualification. The study used under-graduates in the University with GCE certificates.

A study by Muraina, et.al (2010) and Fowowe, et.al (2010) indicated that entry qualification cannot serve as a predictor of the students' academic performance in higher level of education. Okwilagwe (2001) also

argued that there was a very low correlation coefficient between SSCE and academic performance of the Universities' undergraduate students.

Peers and Johnston (1994) also confirmed the validity of the number and grades of passes in the Scottish Certificate of Education in predicting first year and the final year University performance. Gay (1996) also indicated that high school grades could be used to predict the College grades. However, these findings were contrary to O'Rourke, Martin and Hurley's (1989) where the scholastic Aptitude Test (SAT) was unable to predict examination performance as effectively as the Leaving Certificate Examination (LCE) pointed out.

Adeyemi (2008) supported earlier findings on the complexity of students' entry qualification. To him performance varies considerably from one subject to the other. Thus, scholars' conclusions on this issue are based on data collected and so many other factors such as students' attitude (Ali, 1983), institutional factors (Pidgeon, 1970) and home background (Olanipekun, 2012).

Research Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between students' entry qualification in English language and academic performance in General English in Colleges of Education in Kwara State.

Research Question

Is there any difference in the performance of student base on entry qualification in English language and academic performance in General English?

This research work employed descriptive survey method where students' scores in General English along with their entry qualification in English language, were collected and analyzed for the purpose of this study.

The sample population comprises of students from Colleges of Education in Kwara State. Pro-forma was used to collect students' scores from year 1 to year 3 (final year) students of 2011/2012 with a total number of one hundred and eighty six students that were randomly selected.

Research hypothesis and question were tested and answered using Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Co-efficient and descriptive statistic. Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Co-efficient is used to determine the degree of relationship between two set of variables (Okoro, 2002), this could be supported by (Owie, 1996) that, Correlation Co-efficient Method was used to compute the strength of association between variables. Descriptive statistic summarizes a relatively large array of data into meaningful forms such that they could be more easily interpreted (Nkemakolam, 2002).

RESULTS

The result in Table 1 reveals that there is a strong correlation between students' entry qualification in English language and students' academic performance in General English with correlation coefficient of .220. This means that early good academic performance could influence students' academic performance in the College. The hypothesis is thereby rejected.

Table 2 also revealed that students performed better at their students' entry level in English language than in General English when they get to College of Education as the mean scores in the entry qualification is higher than that of General English in the Colleges of Education. In this sense, the research question is answered.

DISCUSSIONS

The relationship between students' entry qualification in English language and academic performance in General English in Colleges of Education in Kwara State.

As seen from the findings of this research, there is a correlation between students' entry qualification in English language and academic performance in General English of students in Colleges of Education in

Kwara State. This therefore posited that there is tendency for students' entry qualification in English language to act as a predictive virile instrument for future academic performance of students in General English.

This Gbore (2013) also pointed out when he was of the opinion that there was moderate correlation coefficient between SSCE and future academic performance of students. The finding also agreed with the findings of WAEC (1992) that a positive and significant relationship exists between candidates' performance in the SSCE and academic performance in tertiary institution. Ojetunde (1988) also articulated a high positive correlation between entry qualification and success. Ubokobong (1993) keenly unfolded those students with high number of credit in Nigeria secondary school examinations as those who performed well in higher institutions

However, Idika (1997), Majasan and Bakare (1979) did not agree with the above findings as revealed in their research when they keenly noted that entry qualification was poor predictor of academic performance and that the degree of performance in the Colleges cannot be linked to the quality of grade obtained in the entry qualification. Adeniyi & Solomon (NY) were of the opinion that there were no significant differences between students' entry qualification and their final academic performance in NCE programmes. This they ascertained through the mean scores of students admitted through Pre- NCE programmes and that of their JAMB counterparts.

It is therefore plausible to unfold that students' academic performance is one of the current educational problem of public interest based on poor level of students' performance especially in public examination and at schools and various higher institutions (kolawole, 1998, kolawole and Dele, 2002) in which English language is not an exemption. This Iwovi, Okebukola and Oladotun (1992) gave credent to when they averred that the problem of under achievement among school children has persisted in many subjects areas such as English language. However, students still perform better in entry qualification in English language than in General English in the Colleges of Education in Kwara State as obtainable from this research.

CONCLUSION

At this juncture, it is jussive to assert that students' entry qualification is an instrument used in predicting higher education. However, while some scholars' works agreed with the outcome of this finding some findings are at variance. It should therefore be noted that the validity of data collected and the institutions under experiment or the environment could go a long way in influencing the summations of various scholars on a subject like.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Teachers of English at all level should endeavor to create in students the urge and the necessary curiosity in learning English language.
2. Students should also desist from all forms of examination malpractices. They should learn to read and face their books, not 'face book' and face examinations without internal, external or foreign assistance, either from their teachers or 'machineries' since early good academic performance could influence later academic performance.

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Table 1: Correlations between General Eng. And Entry Qualification in English language

		General English	EntryQualification
General Eng.	Pearson Correlation	1.090	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.220	
Entry Qualification	N	186	186
	Pearson Correlation	.090	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.220	
	N	186	186

Table 2:

Mean scores of students in General Eng. And Entry Qualification in English language

	Mean	Std. deviation	N
General Eng.	45.403	23.608	37186
EntryQualification	49.258	15.250	28186

